

OSCARS

NGI EXPLORERS' AWARDS CEREMONY

BEST PROJECT EXCELLENCE

BEST NGI EXPLORERS IMPACT

BRIGHTEST EU EXPLORER

BEST SOCIAL INNOVATION IMPACT

FUNDED
BY

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zabala
INNOVATION

AWARDS CATEGORIES & EVALUATION CRITERIA

BEST PROJECT EXCELLENCE

This category reviews what the project idea aims to achieve. The evaluation will consider the motivation for the mission, the project's objectives & concept, and the ambition. An important aspect of being assessed is the novelty and the knowledge gap in the field of interest.

BEST NGI EXPLORERS IMPACT

This category judges the outcomes achieved by the project at the end of the mission in the form of tangible results, including sustainability indicators with the US partner. Examples may include: peer-reviewed papers, technical specifications, software bundles, new services, business/commercial agreements, etc.

BRIGHTEST EU EXPLORER

This category evaluates the individual achievement seized out of the project, looking into how the Explorers' careers benefited from the missions. Examples may include: higher professional status, awards/prizes, new job opportunities/positions.

BEST SOCIAL INNOVATION IMPACT

This category is aligned with the Next Generation Internet vision, analyzing which idea contributed the most to have a positive social impact.

CHANDRA DE KEYSER

PROJECT

Engagement Insights for the “next normal” of video collaboration

FOCUS AREA

AI, digital wellbeing, online collaboration insights

CHALLENGE

Humanity changed habits permanently with Covid-19: people use video collaboration for work from home, eLearning, telemedicine...

Video is massified in the „next normal“.

Our capacity to understand each other is affected as non-verbal represents 70% of human communication.

In face-to-face interactions, we use our emotional intelligence to read facial expressions and body language.

The problem is that our mutual understanding is limited by the format of video platforms.

Therefore, our capacity for fruitful dialogues & productive collaborations is seriously affected: co-workers grow depressed and their colleagues don't notice, students lose motivation, and Doctors miss key elements of their patients' experiences.

KEY RESULTS

- MoodMe developed Vimotion, a Windows application that analyses emotions of participants in video calls.
- It respects privacy as no faces are stored.
- It is ethical & unbiased thanks to gender and ethnical diversity in our datasets.
- Vimotions detects 8 emotions (happy surprise afraid angry contempt disgust sad neutral).
- Anonymized data are sent to MoodMe secure servers on AWS.
- Actionable insights are provided on dashboards and reports showing participants' engagement, emotions trends during a meeting...

IMPACT

1. EQ in video:

- Humanity was caught off-guard by Covid-19. Massive shifts took place abruptly.
- The tools for the „next normal“ of work, learn & health are not adapted to the challenges of remote scenarios.
- People well-being and mental health have been affected profoundly in ways we are not yet comprehending.
- MoodMe solution helps people live happier online video meetings.
- MoodMe provides actionable insights to help people take better decisions with emotional intelligence.

2. Inclusion & Diversity:

- MoodMe empowers organizations to identify and address engagement gaps tied to demographics.
- GREG (Gender Race Engagement Gap) helps Chief Diversity Officers gather objective engagement metrics & highlight inclusion issues.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

- The US collaboration helped us by engaging in top academic settings with all legal, privacy and ethics norms for research with human subjects.
- I enrolled in several courses at Uni. Houston on experiments involving human subjects and passed all exams successfully.
- We will continue our fruitful cooperation by submitting to the IRB to conduct larger real-life experiments with students of several Professors.

FRANZISKA KIRSTEIN

PROJECT

Ethical Guidelines for the Development of AI-supported Healthcare Robots

FOCUS AREA

Artificial Intelligence

CHALLENGE

"Our future is a race between the growing power of technology and the wisdom with which we use it." Stephen Hawking

Combining robotics with artificial intelligence (AI) generates endless new capabilities for robots. This can increase quality of life, but it will also change our society. Research within ethics of AI and robotics addresses this challenge. There is a substantial amount of documentation, thus it can be difficult, costly and time consuming for robotics companies to get a comprehensive view.

KEY RESULTS

- My project created new insights on how ethics can be integrated in robotics and AI development. The case example is the Patient Transfer Rehabilitation Robot. It is currently manually operated by healthcare professionals but will soon be equipped with AI.
- The main result is a toolbox for robotics companies. It highlights why ethics management is important when developing artificially intelligent robots, outlines potential ethical issues and suggests useful literature. Finally, it describes guiding principles on how to avoid and deal with ethical issues, including practical implementation tips. The goal is for everyone in the organization to be qualified in identifying and addressing ethical issues.

IMPACT

- The project results can have major positive impact on our society and the planet, contributing to a better future and increasing our trust in technology.
- The toolbox makes it easier to consider ethical issues concerning e.g., data handling, environmental impact, accountability, diversity, distribution of technology, transparency, and explainability when developing intelligent robots. Reflection, transparency, and the inclusion of all stakeholders in the development process is emphasized. This helps to consider the impact deriving from assigning relevant aspects of society to intelligent robots. The result is the avoidance of negative consequences preventatively rather than after the introduction to society.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

The project expanded my knowledge and network through collaborations with US expert researchers from various disciplines. It created new partnerships and potential customers:

- The robot will be a case story in the US Node's ethics course, possibly leading to further exchange visits/ collaborations.
- The project is part of the US Node's open classroom series on AI and ethics.
- Evaluation studies of the robot are planned.

HASAN SÜZEN

PROJECT

Smart Navigator

FOCUS AREA

Artificial Intelligence

CHALLENGE

The project, Smart Navigator, focuses on developing a novel general system architecture ensuring high-tech accuracy and privacy-preserving solutions, and accordingly exploring a new model for network analysis in algorithmic decision systems. In data-driven world, digital transformation is a must step not an option for both the public and private sectors. Such a transformation certainly requires smart decision systems. In this frame, with its special focus, Smart Navigator offers a hybrid intelligence approach and system architecture as a novel solution to address the challenge of AI in intelligent decision systems such as trustworthiness, explainability, accuracy problems and privacy concerns; further, it provides a new approach to network analysis to detect nodes (events, objects, documents) and to extract relations & patterns with high performance in complex systems.

KEY RESULTS

- A hybrid intelligence-powered system architecture has been developed and initial modules (features) have been deployed to the cloud environment which proves that the system architecture works properly, and the modules (features) run at high performance.
- A novel approach, Multi-Space Analysis Model, to Network Analysis has been developed, several tests were done by using ruled/pattern-based approach, and detection & relation extraction accuracy rates were very high.
- Outputs were published at different platforms. Then the project has been recognized as a deep tech pioneer by Hello Tomorrow in DEC 2021.

IMPACT

- The use of hybrid intelligence to address the challenges of AI (trustworthiness, explainability, accuracy problems and privacy concerns), especially in complex systems, has huge potential to fill a gap in the field and open new windows for further studies. Especially for strategic sectors, namely energy, finance & banking, healthcare, security; such a hybrid intelligence-powered decision system could drive the digital transformation. Further, the new approach to network analysis can make great impact on anomaly, treat, risk, opportunity detection and provide automated solutions in healthcare and other strategic domains.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

The expedition has provided a very fertile and collaborative ground for exploring new ideas, concepts, and methodologies for the project; and exchanging know-how and experience for further studies and next phases of Smart Navigator.

IGOR KOTSIUBA

PROJECT
HEALTHYMITY

FOCUS AREA
Artificial Intelligence

CHALLENGE

Being mostly focused on cybersecurity iSolutions Labs with this project HEALTHYMITY defined two problems of health sector: The information from wearables, diagnostic tools and doctor's archive is not fused for decision support thus it has limited impact on patients health. Second problem is that according to the national, EU, US and privacy regulations sharing of data is limited. HEALTHYMITY breaks down those silos through federated learning approach, so we can enable interoperability of patients' data both in the US and EU, adoption of explainable AI and data fusion in hospitals and support integration of all those amazing projects already funded in EU and the USA enabling safe and secure information sharing without actual sharing of sensitive information.

KEY RESULTS

- During this collaboration I embraced all the best practices the US node Santa Clara University developed during this pandemic situation and innovation to the market roadmap. EU has outstanding results both from EU funded and market innovation activities. I brought a small piece of understanding how quickly we can achieve impact on society and keep high level of innovation and intellectual merits.
- I had meetings with Sky Deck Barkley, USAID, Embassy of Ukraine, Stanford University, Sonoma University, travelled to many states in the USA to meet governors, entrepreneurs, investors, expats from EU and successful stories authors to discuss and find the exploitation path for us EU based innovators to stay home and work globally.

IMPACT

- Within a top-notch infrastructure of Santa Clara University and collaboration with PhD students who are top engineers in Facebook, Cisco, Microsoft and Uber it is a short path to find both strength and weaknesses of all our projects and ideas we do in Europe.
- Testbed of technology in the US is a timely and the quickest way to crush test and pivot the idea.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

NGI Explorer program is a fantastic Eco system and family. I met all 3 cohorts of explorers both physically and virtually. We participate together at various platforms, forums and conferences as one united family. We share ideas, help each other and facilitate our journey after the program. Being in the USA I met key stakeholders there and we plan a scientific collaboration with NSF, Ukraine, EU, and the UK. From the USA. NGI Explorer is a program which puts you in a "right family of parents, mentors and advisors, add highly relevant brothers and sisters and buys a ticket to life changing trip"

LUKASZ PORWOL

PROJECT

VR-Dialogue – AI & VR driven Next-Generation Online Communication

FOCUS AREA

Artificial Intelligence

CHALLENGE

VR-Dialogue focuses on enabling the XR Metaverse researchers and businesses to make better data-driven decisions in designing the Next Generation Internet serious communication layer. In the face of growing demand for remote work and education, VR-Dialogue provides a highly affordable and accessible serious VR & AI-driven communication analytics platform and supports more engaged and efficient online interactions.

KEY RESULTS

- Designed and deployed a ready for service, AI-driven VR-communication research platform
- Delivered a privacy-aware, VR group-interaction-level analytics framework allowing live discussion feedback and rich insights postprocessing.
- Conducted validation and AI-training sessions combined with dissemination and publishing efforts that helped establish extended collaborations
- Generated novel findings submitted to a scientific journal
- Contributed to MIT Reality Hack spin-off – Reality Fest – VR online event
- Got awarded participation at AWE 2020 in California – engaged with top talent and business in XR domain
- Two industrial grant proposals submitted – extension to VR-Dialogue (Facebook and Sony)
- Submitted Horizon Europe proposals on Ethics in XR: CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-28 and XR and New Media: CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-06

IMPACT

- Our Open-Source, WebXR standard-based platform enables affordable, full cloud access (no installation required) and simultaneous research session hosting 24/7 for Metaverse researchers and developers anywhere in the world.
- To our knowledge, this is one of the first attempts at building an AI-driven VR analytics infrastructure to study serious online engagements. Our group-behaviour level analytics framework not only preserves user privacy but also eliminates the need for specialised expensive VR headsets with additional sensors.
- We started collaborations with an extended circle of researchers in the USA (Harvard University) and Israel. We run collaborative online sessions and engaged in funds acquisition for further studies and extension of the VR-Dialogue platform.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

The US collaboration significantly widened the perspectives and experiences of VR-Dialogue communication research. The explorer benefited from strong immersion in a Boston environment that extended beyond the node – Simmons University, US-node, through its network, supported the explorer in linking with researchers at MIT and Harvard University and fostered further collaboration. The explorer is now a lead at the organizing team of MIT Reality Hack – the world's largest XR hackathon at MIT.

TUDOR BALINISTEANU

PROJECT

Visual Identities of Virtual Agents with Empathy Traits (VIVAET)

FOCUS AREA

Artificial Intelligence & HealthTech

CHALLENGE

We aim to create human-AI sense-react habitats capable of enabling maximally empathic human-AI interaction. We have begun developing neuroscience and psychology experiments that involve physical human-AI haptic coupling to determine the visual identity of the AI (a face) capable of extracting the maximum of empathic response from a particular human user. At the next stage of our collaborative work, extending beyond the end of the NGI explorers grant tenure, we will use machine-learning algorithms to fine tune the AI's awareness of individual human users needs involved in eliciting human empathic responses.

KEY RESULTS

We built a human-AI haptic coupling system prototype. This consists of the bas-relief of a human palm layered with sensors that collect data regarding a human's empathic response to a face that is simultaneously displayed as the AI's visual identity. Software was created to group collected data into data sets (on which the AI would be trained to find patterns of human empathy response). The sensors collect HRV, GSR, and peripheral skin temperature data. We have yet to integrate an EEG sensor collecting P300 signal and a portable pupillometer recording pupil diameter change.

IMPACT

Creating an AI module designed to extract the maximal empathic response from a human user will have tremendous importance for designing complex medical AIs. When world-wide efforts to create such medical AIs will become integrated, we will be able to contribute a module that will make that medical AI more empathic, with positive consequences in terms of relieving stress at triage points in hospitals and clinics, performing remote or at-home diagnoses, not to mention increasing confidence and trust in human users of such AIs. Furthermore, our research is applicable beyond health settings, as it can be implemented in a wide range of services settings, from public social services to banking services, or hubs along transport networks, or long-haul activities that are isolating for human users of an accompanying AI (i.e. long-haul transport, marine scientific expeditions, or, indeed, space flight).

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

We are in the process of formalising and institutionalising our partnership between University of Suceava, Romania, IT Lisbon, and NMSU, USA by incorporating a spin-off entity. This will be 50% owned by our US partner, and 50% owned by Romanian partners. We have begun applying for funding as a consortium, in the first instance submitting a joint application for funding to the EIC Pathfinder Challenge, Awareness Inside, and we have plans for future NSF and ERC joint funding proposal submissions.

ALEXANDER NORTA

PROJECT

Self-sovereign multi-factor identity authentication using smart-contract blockchain technology

FOCUS AREA

Multi-factor identity authentication

CHALLENGE

This project focused on multi-factor challenge set self-sovereign identity authentication (MFSSIA). Single sign on identity authentication is not sufficient any longer for the complex multi-faceted cross-organizational socio-technical collaboration scenarios of a rising machine-to-everything (M2X) economy.

KEY RESULTS

○ Deliverable 1

The establishment of a relevant socio-technical running case about e-healthcare for elderly monitoring inspired by the M-Sec Santander project where the focus rests on health-monitoring elderly with IoT devices.

○ Deliverable 2

Specifying assurance-authentication levels extended from OMB 04-04 together with technical requirements recommended by NIST 800-63. Additionally, we further clarify the authentication levels for multi-factor authentication (MFA) and also map the protocol into the running case of the M-Sec elderly monitoring case. Furthermore, we clarify in risk-assessment procedures that hacking methods may breach respective security levels.

○ Deliverable 3

We explore MFSSIA challenge sets in the Authcoin identity-authentication protocol while taking the running case of Deliverable 1 into account for risk-based authentication. Attack vectors against biometric authentication we also explore since the latter presents itself as the most convenient for elderly people.

○ Deliverable 4

This deliverable shows simple use cases for identity authentication of elderly persons for health surveillance in the Deliverable 1 use case context where the assumption is members of organizations engage in collaborations cross-organizationally connecting their systems.

IMPACT

The main impact is that the work performed in the NGI explorers project has raised the attention of the ONTOCHAIN project that has awarded in their Call #2 funding for an implementation of Authcoin for an extension of their existing technology stack.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

Based on the first project deliverable with the running case, we have shared interests as in Florida, the partners Prof David Mohaisen and Prof. Murat Yuksel, work in parallel on a similar project proposal. Thus, that way we see the scope to publish the MFSSIA results in several papers.

ALEXANDRU PANAIT

PROJECT

Decentralized Public Administration

FOCUS AREA

Blockchain

CHALLENGE

The error rate of the current system of government is directly proportional to the level of citizens understanding and applicability of the laws. Due to high non digital data and the level of complexity of the legal acts, checking the blackholes in the system is extremely expensive, so covering the errors of the system by legal means of correction is unsustainable due to the high costs.

The current bureaucratic system cannot scale efficiently by hiring more officials, as this only helps increase the chaos of entropy.

KEY RESULTS

- The white paper developed in this expedition presents the main pillars through which the state can move to a fully digital and decentralized government, using blockchain technology.
- History teaches us that using blockchain technology in the financial system is redundant because it cannot scale in terms of transaction speed to meet the need for instant trading. Instead, we use the immutability and security property of a blockchain system to provide secured and transparent governance solutions. Thus, by moving paperwork into digital structures through smart contracts, all data about citizens will be managed efficiently, and the procedures can even be fully automated using law smart contracts.

IMPACT

Documents can be moved from the current format to a digital format based on smart contracts templates for each type of document/ life event. This way we can even achieve the automation of institutional procedures and reduce the waiting time of the citizens. This automatization is applicable even for laws and their procedures. This way we can reduce the level of human error. Even the necessary staff can be reduced.

Thus, many laws can become digital, and all the data that the state has about citizens will be used in accordance with digital legislation. New laws can be introduced in this system through smart contracts. All the laws can be applied automatically on citizens data using smart procedures.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

The collaboration with Arizona State University was an excellent one and together we want to publish the white paper I developed, in order to access some funding for the development of the technology.

DIMITAR KYOSEV

PROJECT

Cross-border regulatory coordination and enforcement of blockchain assets

FOCUS AREA

Blockchain

CHALLENGE

- What?:
In the words of the EU's Blockchain strategy our challenge is promoting legal certainty. This aims to "increase investments and to ensure consumer and investor protection."
- Why?:
The way the global economy works is at a flux point. The ability to create trust over large distances in a cross-border settings - e.g. blockchain - is a game changer on multiple levels. For it to live to its true potential, however, certainty off-the-chain needs to match the one on-chain.
- In a nutshell?
We are looking at the ability investors to be effectively protected (from abuse) through regulatory action in a blockchain (cross-border) context.

KEY RESULTS

- How?:
We have outlined a blueprint for a voluntary standard that would provide enforceable protections for investors in blockchain financial assets.
- Why?:
The only way to create regulatory enforcement on the chain is for the smart contract to have it hard-wired. Further a voluntary standard reflects the EU (digital) values.
- Why would people use it?:
Investors want to enjoy protections. Blockchain projects will be incentivized to offer that. The business model we have developed under the tutoring of NGI TETRA ensures that the financial incentives for all parties are aligned, while the technical blocks remains free to use by the blockchain projects.

IMPACT

- Economic impact?
The estimate for the size of the crypto market by 2030 is \$4 trillion [Source: Allied Market Research, Crypto Currency Market - 2030] The infusion of investment in the space (creating growth and jobs) needs to be facilitated by multiple factors, one of which is legal certainty.
- Other?
There are three major models for regulating the crypto markets - the American, the Chinese and the European. The standard promotes the European values (like owning one's own data) as they create a human-centric approach, rather than top-down attitude.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

- Why the US node?
The NMSU Team has developed a groundbreaking method for retroactively updating information on the chain (enabling technical enforcement of taxation and court orders).
- Cross-disciplinary approach?
In NGI Explorers we were able to really take the best of legal and IT and create a value-driven opensource result.

DIXON VIMALAJEEWA

PROJECT

Block chain for climate-neutral agriculture

FOCUS AREA

Blockchain

CHALLENGE

There is an urgent need to scale up on the global response towards implementing actions against carbon emission (CE). Even though modern technologies facilitate corrective actions against CE, poor transfer and sharing of such knowledge amongst the community, increases the lack of awareness in taking timely measures against CE. A collaborative approach is, therefore, essential, not only for providing more practical and credible information to reduce CE but also to build awareness and knowledge sharing initiatives focused on reducing CE.

KEY RESULTS

In order to promote the uptake of timely initiatives and enforce measures to minimize CE, a Block Chain (BC)-based knowledge transformation platform was proposed to share reliable information about CE reduction strategies as well as benefits that can be acquired through minimizing CE in the context of agriculture.

- Explored Carbon Emission Potentials: explored the carbon emission potentials of various agriculture activities and actions taken to reduce CE and their benefits in terms of cost.
- Developed Carbon Coins: information from step 1 was used to develop two models to compute CE reduction score and rewarded credit (as in CO2 coins) value based on the contribution to reducing CE.
- Developed Smart Contract: Developed a smart contract (SC) combining the two models including services such as registering users in the BC system, transferring credits between users, updating data stored in the BC, and accessing information shared over the BC system and then deployed and then published in an existing Ethereum BC platform.

IMPACT

- Sharing Knowledge and get Rewarded: registered users can access the SC through the BC platform to share credible carbon reduction information transparently, earn CO2 coins as rewards and utilize their credits.
- Availability and Accessibility of Credible Information: outside users can actively utilize the BC platform and explore different actions taken by users to reduce CE and benefits that they have gained in terms of their CE reduction score and CO2 coin value and get motivated to be a contributor to CE reduction as a result.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

My US partner had a clear vision about essential requirements in developing BS systems for a wide range of applications so that I received proper guidance and instructions to successfully finish my expedition. This collaboration was a great chance to put together our knowledge and gain new experience as a result.

EFSTATHIOS MITSKAS

PROJECT

Non-Fungible Tokens

FOCUS AREA

Blockchain

CHALLENGE

The main purpose of this project was to investigate the NFT market that already exists today, spot any limitations and propose a different architecture/system in terms of scalability and cost efficiency.

Main focus was given on security as well as the user friendliness of a solution.

KEY RESULTS

A custom architecture was proposed and a mobile application was created to allow the community engage with the NFTs. Also, the NFT smart contract is open source and accessible from the community.

IMPACT

The open source smart contract is accesible and ready to be used from the blockchain community as a starting point for creating an NFT marketplace. The research documents created are also considered to be valuable for the community and people that want to operate in the NFT space.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

The US experience helped me grow a lot as a person. I got to collaborate with blockchain engineers and exchange knowledge. This made me more confident working on my project as well as making the right decisions on it.

FERNANDO GÓMEZ GIL

PROJECT

Transforming the future of employment with a trust-enhancing internet technology

FOCUS AREA

Blockchain

CHALLENGE

Students' and professionals' exchange between the EU and the US is gaining in value due to the distinct benefits for all parties involved.

With around 85% of yet not existing jobs of 2030, Internet is the tool to transform the recruitment and training process.

Moreover, between 25-50.000\$ is the cost yearly of bad recruitments due to that 30% of the CVs tell blatant lies.

KEY RESULTS

To facilitate this exchange, and mobility in general, we have developed a Training Experience (TX) platform based on blockchain technology. The TX platform allows matching candidates with companies, universities, foundations, official bodies or even the EURES based on the candidates' professional CVs that are generated automatically.

Above all, the TX platform enables quick documents exchange procedures between universities and companies worldwide and thus considerably fastens any documents-verification processes, with no need for Apostille.

Such standardised verification process of diplomas, CVs and work-related certificates can strongly contribute to the students' and professionals' mobility in the USA and the EU.

Moreover, universities will have statistics to take decisions and to improve the diplomas adapting to the needs of the job market.

IMPACT

In 2025 there will be 262 million students looking for internships whose documents will have to be managed.

In addition, the TX platform allows grouping and publishing grants of different scopes: local, regional, national and European, for which job seekers can apply.

Moreover, due to the cryptocurrencies we developed, universities and sponsors will be able to create grant programs for their students and therefore encourage more exchange and increase the mobility between the respective countries.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

We were able to develop the blockchain-based platform and learnt more about the data protection law, types of jobs/internships contracts, and, most importantly, ways to access the market. We improved our knowledge about the job culture of the USA and are now able to compare/adapt old standards or create new ones

We are still working on improving our system preparing the personalization of the platform for each university. We hope with these new updates we will be able to attract more universities to our platform because the success of our blockchain validation system is the massive adoption.

MAIOL VALENTÍ BERTRAN

PROJECT

Technical improvement of Blockchain of Things devices

FOCUS AREA

Blockchain, IoT

CHALLENGE

Data exchanged on IoT devices and in Industry 4.0 is frequently targeted by hackers. One-third of AI projects provide ineffective or dangerous results due to the manipulation of their data. This affects many industries: Automotive, Healthcare, Industry 4.0, Smart Cities, etc. Fraud in these datasets endangers human lives, compromises democracy, damages business assets, and degrades the environment.

We have developed a family of ultra-low cost hardware devices (Blockchain-of-Things devices -BoT-d) that connect directly to IoT devices and secure each of the data coming from them by linking to a Blockchain transaction, making each piece of the data traceable and unforgeable from their origin.

KEY RESULTS

- Good optimization of the two devices that we have focused on: Raspberry Pi 0 and Raspberry Pi 4 B.
- Possibility of considering the incorporation of batteries to free up the devices from being connected to the power supply, thanks to optimization.
- Decentralised KMS (key management system) to protect and manage sensible data: passwords, endpoints, permissions... in the devices.
- Write to Blockchain without an intermediate server to process data.
- Possibility to use different Blockchains: Ethereum, IOTA and BigchainDB.
- Robust software and good architecture. Use of (Docker, TDD, logging system...).
- Versatile product that can handle many more projects that we expected thanks to the software and the optimization that we achieved.
- Reduce the cost of writing to Ethereum.
- Monetary management and control of the devices.

IMPACT

This solution targets different markets: Automotive, Energy, Healthcare, Smart Manufacturing, Smart Retail, Smart Buildings, Smart Homes, and Smart Cities. Even more, this system can protect personal, sensible data. In addition, it may be used to secure against deep-fakes, by protecting streams of audio and video simultaneously against manipulation.

Main types of customers:

- Device manufacturers using the data generated to train AI systems or market that data to other companies.
- Companies interested in buying/using IoT data from third parties.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

- Contacts to USA.
- The quality of the project and the product improves.
- New implementations/recommendations for the project that you might not have expected.
- New market possibilities in the USA.
- New experience, new ways of working, different culture, good universities and professors...
- Everything is a learning experience and a big improvement at any level.

RUI COSTA

PROJECT

GoGreen - Improving sustainable transportation via green behaviours

FOCUS AREA

Blockchain

CHALLENGE

Sustainability plays a crucial role in everyone's life. It affects everyone directly, and most of the time, only a few people care about it and understand that even a small gesture can have a tremendous effect on everyone's lives. It is one of the core missions of Ubiwhere to make the world more sustainable. For that to happen, we need societal, environmental and behavioural changes. We aim to help people understand the impact of small gestures on their communities through technology.

KEY RESULTS

The team has managed to develop the GoGreen solution that consists of a digital rewarding mechanism based on Blockchain technology, making use of open standards and open APIs for easy data exchange and integration with existing or third-party applications. The aim is to create awareness about GHG emissions and encourage people to use the most sustainable means through incentives and by validating their choices using the GoGreen application.

With these rewarding mechanisms, we are validating the solution with the Portland community and assessing these rewards' impact on their behaviour by validating their choices using the GoGreen app in a trustworthy manner that ensures data privacy.

IMPACT

The solution impacts in several ways the society, the environment and the local economy namely:

- CO2 emissions reduction by promoting sustainable means and incentivising users to opt for them;
- Data for city management by collecting information on the mobility patterns;
- Promoting citizens engagement by providing a solution that enables citizens to get detailed information about their carbon footprint;
- Environmental awareness by providing dashboards where any citizen can see their daily decisions and impact on the environment;
- Contribute to the local economy by engaging local businesses.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

The reality in the US is very different from the one in Europe, in terms of culture, habits, needs, topography, interests, among others. Developing the GoGreen solution together with URBAN.SYSTEMS allowed us to gain new knowledge and perspective regarding the US citizens' needs. URBAN.SYSTEMS supported Ubiwhere by providing the critical mass that allowed the system to thrive, collaborating on the definition and customisation of the rewarding scheme while promoting GoGreen via their robust network of partners.

STAVROS ANTONIADIS

PROJECT

The Sovereignty of Medical Data

FOCUS AREA

Blockchain

CHALLENGE

Identifiers these days are centralized and susceptible to any kind of misuse and malfunction by anyone rather than only their rightful owner. The use of blockchain can solve this problem by creating an immutable and persistent identifier registered on the blockchain that is controlled only by its owner through its bound public key (decentralized identifiers). By using these identifiers as a base layer, this project introduces medical results in the form of a verifiable credential bound to the user identifier, which enhances portability.

KEY RESULTS

The outcomes of this expedition was a set of smart contract actions that follows the DIDs and VCs specifications (DID services) and a wallet app that integrates with it in order to give to the users an interface to perform the following capabilities:

- create a did,
- update a did,
- create a vc (Covid Test results),
- validate a vc

Furthermore, a document that describes the characteristics (costs, finality, scalability) of the prevailing solutions was written. In this document, we decided to look deeper into Cosmos, Polkadot, EOS, Ethereum, and Ethereum L2 solutions (Arbitrum and Optimism) and eventually select the most suitable for our use case. Finally, one more document that gives an overview of the pros and cons of the current proposed SSI framework and a comparison between physical identities, digital identities, and SSI framework was written.

IMPACT

This research is considered to be valuable for future researchers who want to dig into this topic, thus, adding value to the DID and VC community and in general to those who want to start their journey in the Blockchain space. Also, the implemented system gives an easy and transparent way to health centers to issue health credentials. This removes the control that health centers have on citizens' identifiers. And also, gives citizens a way to keep their health data secure and easily accessible.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

Living in a foreign country for an extended period of time was a first-time experience for me and also a very fruitful one. Getting to know other cultures meet new people really helps you grow as a person. Also, meeting their work ethics was also really insightful.

AKRAM HAKIRI

PROJECT

SmartNet: Building an Intelligent System for Cognitive Edge Network Programmability and Autonomous Adaptability

FOCUS AREA

Cloud/Edge Computing

CHALLENGE

In the next five years, we expect new services ranging from a small group of users, such as self-assembling robots, to mass-market services, such as mixed holographic reality, cellular-connected drones, autonomous supply chain, and massive twinning. Such services need a data-driven network architecture that can forecast and predict future network states in real-time. However, current networks collect historical data for later analyze of the network behavior. To address these challenges, SmartNet develops the future cognitive and autonomic edge network service orchestration, control and management for achieving resilient 5G/6G internet services by ensuring high availability, openness, and disruption tolerance. SmartNet has the potential to uncover new challenges and inform new solutions, e.g., for federated learning in heterogeneous operating environments spanning the spectrum of resources from the user to the edge to the cloud.

KEY RESULTS

- Demonstrate and validate our advanced AI/ML techniques to support future IoT/6G networks for real-time massive data analysis.
- Develop and evaluate a blockchain system to enforce the security and Trustworthy 5G Massive IoT Network.
- Jointly publishing two research articles and a book chapter with the US partner.
- Organizing BIOC'21 workshop in conjunction with US-EU partners.

IMPACT

- Contributions to standards: Our active collaboration is maintained for developing the future standard for IEEE P1930.1.

- interoperablesolutions: develop interoperable solutions and joint demonstrators between US and EU (COSMOS and chameleon cloud) testbeds.
- Socio-economic: Gathering the value chain including researchers, developers, local authorities, and established open networks to reach out SMEs to prospect of potential commercialization.
- Technology development: the project is a flagship for the future 6G vision to connect human, physical, and digital worlds with a set of 6G key enabling technologies and advances the knowledge beyond the state-of-the-art in building open cognitive models for future NGI.
- Scientific impact: Open the way towards introducing an EU-US ecosystem of top researchers, hi-tech start-ups/SMEs and Internet-related communities collaborating on the evolution of the Internet to bring breakthrough in tomorrow's Internet programmes.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

- Develop commercial opportunities through joint innovation and IPR development and attract world-class partners from telecom sector and future 5G/6G enabled industries.
- Build reputations and establish leadership positions in 5G/6G research and teaching and enables a reinforced collaboration and increased synergies between the NGI and the tomorrow's Internet programmes.
- Realizing financial sustainability by submitting a joint NSF-NGI Atlantic proposal to address the future 6G satellite architecture.
- Open the ways towards future exchange of researchers and internships of master and PhD students and joint data repositories.

ALEXIOS FOURLIS

PROJECT

Edge P.A.T. (Personal Allergy Tracer)

FOCUS AREA

Edge computing

CHALLENGE

Allergic Rhinitis(AR) is a major and growing global health problem. When uncontrolled, it may cause sleep impairment and undermine school performance and work productivity resulting in a disproportional socio-economic burden. Early recognition and monitoring of symptoms are the way to establish management of the AR. Most attempts to engage patients in observing and documenting their symptoms have failed. On the other hand, symptoms' overestimation leads to overtreatment and increases medical costs. Thus, we developed a Machine Learning(ML) algorithm able to perform gestures recognition and correlate them with AR common symptoms with the use of a wearable device.

KEY RESULTS

We managed to optimize the ML model in a way to fit and run on a wearable device in order to provide literally real time results to users. Before the expedition, the system was forced to send raw IMU data to cloud systems to be processed and return the results. This might seem as a pure technical detail but it creates technical complexity leading to an expensive and not feasible business case. Thus, the collaboration with the US node allows us to enhance the value of our service and overcome the aforementioned technical obstacles.

IMPACT

Today, 70 million Europeans suffer from chronic asthma and 100 million from allergic rhinitis. Among them, it is estimated that a significant percentage suffer from a severe form of allergic disease, insufficiently controlled with existing medication, which affects their productivity and quality of life. Edge PAT provide better healthcare services since it is able to notify allergiologists when a treatment is not efficient enough or when an AR outbreak is about to come, without asking any input from patients. To this end, we offer a clinical decision support system that can be a game changer regarding monitoring AR patients since it is unrestrained from the subjective and often misleading patients' input.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

I had the chance to collaborate with experts in the field of ML and took advantage of state-of-the-art equipment of Santa Clara University facilities, which allow me to achieve the objectives set from the beginning. Moreover, we have created a strong partnership that continues after NGI project end.

KANIKA SHARMA

PROJECT

Using federated learning to optimize the placement of distributed services on opportunistic clusters of moving vehicles

FOCUS AREA

Cloud/Edge Computing

CHALLENGE

The project focused on studying the feasibility of using vehicles and roadside units (RSUs) for deploying data collection and processing services. The project provides an Internet of Vehicle (IoV) ecosystem that can collect data using the embedded sensors on moving vehicles as well as process the data using the onboard units on vehicles. We used the data from the intersection-based testbed at the US node at UTC to introduce a Federated Learning-based object detection application to increase the safety of cyclists and pedestrians.

KEY RESULTS

- The solution for the IoV ecosystem has been made more realistic and robust using the video data from the testbed at the US node.
- The mobility model for detecting vehicular flows and vehicle density has been made more robust with the help of transport experts at the US node.
- An AI-based, data-centric, federated learning scheme has been proposed to implement an object-detection application to increase the safety of cyclists and pedestrians.

IMPACT

- Technological advancements of the project:

Vehicular edge/fog computing is a novel computing paradigm to leverage vehicles as infrastructure. The proposed solution provides a prototype for utilizing dynamic networks as infrastructure for implementing distributed, novel, and data-intensive applications.

Our project provides a solution for estimating the mobility pattern of vehicles to study traffic conditions in urban city centers without the need for installing additional infrastructure.

The project also makes an advance in exploring AI for computer vision in a vehicular environment.
- Societal Impact:

For policy makers, this system can provide insights into usage patterns and congestions conditions in urban city centers and freeways. The model also reduces the CAPEX costs by minimizing the need to install additional edge servers for building smart cities.

The work also focuses on building safer roads for commuters by deploying object detection applications for detecting vulnerable pedestrians and cyclists.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

The US node provided a state-of-the-art testbed with video cameras, audio, LIDARs at intersections. They also provided a strong team with expertise in transport systems and the application of computer vision in vehicular environments.

KRASIMIR NIKOLOV

PROJECT

Utilizing 5G and Edge Computing to accelerate adoption of XR (AR/VR) technologies

FOCUS AREA

Cloud/Edge Computing

CHALLENGE

Augmented and Virtual Reality (XR) has shown a lot of potential, especially in Enterprise use cases like Remote work, 3D design, Architecture, Industrial training, etc. However, current XR solutions are difficult to use, and come with lots of limitations - what apps can I use on which XR platform, or can I transfer over my workflow from my Personal Computer to XR? From the Enterprise standpoint, current XR solutions are not scalable and are lacking important Enterprise features like device management, security policies, etc.

We address these shortcomings by Streaming XR applications from the Cloud. Instead of a fractured ecosystem of many different XR platforms and applications, Enterprise can now utilize a SAAS service, which is a more familiar solution for our customers.

KEY RESULTS

Working with our US partner, Orange Silicon Valley (OSV), we were able to validate the use of 5G and Edge Computing in order to address the shortcomings of current XR solutions, thus accelerating the adoption of XR technologies in the Enterprise space. During the Expedition we accomplished the 3 major objectives:

1. Design and develop Proof of Concept applications demonstrating the benefits of XR in key areas like architecture, manufacturing, design, and tourism.
2. Define the required technological stack and architecture that works for both the US and European markets.
3. Define the commercial applications in Europe with highest potential to benefit from XR technologies with focus on Business, and the Enterprise (the way people work). We found tremendous advantages of using XR in many areas like Remote work, Industrial and Architectural design, Education, Mental health and others.

IMPACT

Through utilizing 5G and Edge Computing, we are able to make XR use cases more accessible to the public and more affordable, manageable, and scalable for Enterprises to implement. Right now, XR is an incredible technology which is limited to a few people. Our solution is democratizing access to this new exciting medium. We also focused on industries which are well established in both Europe and the US.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

This type of Streaming solution is possible for the first time thanks to 5G and Edge Computing. Working with our US partner, we were able to create a solution for the next generation of mobile networks which works both in the US and Europe, thus increasing the collaboration across the Atlantic. Furthermore, Orange has different business units in both continents, so this partnership creates more business opportunities in the future.

RICKARD BRÄNNVALL

PROJECT

Privacy Preserving AI and Computation at Edge Data Centers under Homomorphic Encryption

FOCUS AREA

Cloud/Edge Computing

CHALLENGE

FHE has moved from theory to practical application in the last decade, but wide adaption is still constrained by 1) technical difficulty, as it operates under a non-conventional programming paradigm (e.g., slightly different control-structures), and 2) it is computational very demanding. The challenge was to design algorithms for data centre resource provisioning and load balancing that can operate efficiently under FHE.

KEY RESULTS

Algorithmic descriptions were developed for six different machine learning components (Decision tree, Linear regression, Logistic regression, Neural network and Exponentially Weighted Moving Average time-series model), as well as the Homomorphically encrypted argmin function. These were implemented in the Rust programming language and shared as open source on GitHub. Results from the project are already disseminated as an extended abstract published and presented at the 9th Swedish Workshop on Data Science (SweDS2021) in December 2021.

IMPACT

FHE technologies can promote Trustworthy AI by offering Privacy-by-Design, such that both private individuals and business can benefit more from AI-based services since data-confidentiality hurdles can more easily be overcome. We noted much interest in the technology when presenting the work to internal and external audiences, for example when invited to speak at a research hearing on Privacy-by-design at the Swedish Government Authority for Privacy Protection in December.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

It was an invaluable opportunity for researchers with complementing competencies but shared interests to work together on-site in the US during a focused and intense NGI Explorers expedition. We have many ideas for future work and areas for further collaboration. A comprehensive manuscript based on the work is already in preparation targeting submission to a major CS conference this spring.

MOHIT TANEJA

PROJECT

Allocation of Fog Resources to IoT Edge Devices

FOCUS AREA

Cloud/Edge Computing

CHALLENGE

With more devices onboard the Internet every day, there is a constant drive to balance QoS with efficient use of resources. In the IoT era, these devices along the things-to-cloud continuum, present a unique opportunity to additionally serve as computing hubs. Termed Fog computing, this paradigm can be used to host applications and process data closer to the source.

- The challenge is to use the computing resources available on these devices in an efficient manner without affecting their natural working and keeping a balance between under and over utilization.
- The project focused on developing AI and optimization methods to achieve an efficient and dynamic allocation of fog resources in such environments.

KEY RESULTS

- One of the key findings of the work is the use of residual LSTM based deep learning approach that gives an efficient and improved forecasting model for dynamic resource management compared to the existing state-of-the-art approaches.
- Further, the approach developed can be applied to other such latency critical use-cases and environments. The work is interoperable and transferable to other IoT verticals and use-cases. Two joint publications published in IEEE GHTC 2021 and IEEE CCNC 2022.

IMPACT

- Contribution to the Next Generation Network: Development and validation of a deep learning based efficient and lightweight resource allocation and forecasting model with real-world data
- Interoperable Solution: Development of interoperable integrated platform solution for real-time resource management in dynamic environments
- Scalable solution having a data engineering pipeline with no additional overheads for deployment in the production environment

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

- One of the key collaboration benefits is the global knowledge exchange through interactions with the team in US and team in EU. This knowledge exchange and collaboration has resulted into the experimentation and scientific analysis performed on the selected use-case, along with development of new ideas.
- NGI Explorers programs gave a platform that led to continued collaboration beyond the program in other areas of mutual interest, which includes smart agriculture and applied analytics. The collaboration is still going on with potential of expanding the collaborative team through available funding streams and doing research exchange of team members through the same.

REFAEL SHAMIR

PROJECT

Privacy-aware Health Sensing, Inferencing, and Remote Monitoring

FOCUS AREA

Cloud/Edge Computing

CHALLENGE

Remote health services, these days, are required now more than ever and the last few years provide us with several catalysts to revisit existing challenges and address new ones.

With the rise of digital wearable health products (e.g., smartwatches) as a consumer product, we now have a view into a new realm of possibilities in better surveying various physical health aspects of a large population at once, given centralized computing as an industry norm. However, with the rising concerns over privacy, and private information sharing at a large scale, new legislations are undergoing revisions (e.g., HIPAA, FDA in the US) and new ones being manifested (e.g., GDPR, MDR in Europe) to address such challenges.

KEY RESULTS

A new paradigm that will consider privacy-awareness instead of a mass collection of data, as a top priority was put forward. This said paradigm can be broken down into the following:

- Suggesting a decentralized computation scheme, including architectural design, algorithm development, and software implementation for technical POC purposes
- Obfuscation of privileged data that can identify an individual using advanced cryptographic schemes

IMPACT

Both technological and social impacts can be observed. Technology-wise, we can oversee an improvement in supporting early intervention, adapting hospital infrastructure/staff, and more refined geographic mapping, all by introducing a novel survey tool coupled with edge computing and a privacy-first approach. On the other hand, we find alignment with two (2) UN SDG in Good Health & Wellbeing and Affordable and Clean Energy.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

This project has been jointly executed by a European organization (Nyurobeat UG, a.k.a. Letos) and the University of Oregon, namely with the Centre of Cyber Security and Privacy (CCSP). The European end contributed knowledge of hardware design, and scientific related domain expertise in the fields of physiology, whereas the US end contributed knowledge of Internet of Things, and scientific related domain expertise in the fields of privacy-awareness.

Going forward, we intend to submit a joint publication to relevant conferences/journals as well as explore the expansion of this project from the home environment to the office environment (relevant team members were identified).

DENIS DONADEL

PROJECT

A Fingerprinting-Based Countermeasure Against EVSE Relay Attacks

FOCUS AREA

Cybersecurity

CHALLENGE

To support the increasing spread of electric vehicles, charging stations are being built worldwide. The new generation of charging stations employs the Vehicle-To-Grid (V2G) paradigm, exploiting novel standards such as the ISO 15118. This standard enables high-level communication between the vehicle and the charging column, helps manage the charge smartly, and simplifies the payment phase. However, the integration of intelligent computing and the interconnection of Smart Grid with external networks open new vulnerability surfaces, increased even more by the novelty of such charging paradigms.

In this project, we present EVExchange, the first relay attack to steal energy during a charging session in a V2G communication: i.e., charging the attacker's car while letting the victim pay for it. Furthermore, if reverse charging flow is enabled, the attacker can even sell the energy available on the victim's car! Thus, getting the economic profit of this selling, and leaving the victim with a completely discharged battery.

KEY RESULTS

We started by developing a virtual testbed using MiniV2G to prove the effectiveness of the attack in stealing the energy. Moreover, we build a physical testbed to validate the attack in a more realistic scenario.

Then, we propose a lightweight modification of the ISO 15118 protocol to prevent the attack by including a distance bounding algorithm. This countermeasure is transparent to the user and prevents relay attacks before sharing sensitive information. Finally, we validated the countermeasure on both our testbeds.

IMPACT

This research is important for the cybersecurity of the electric vehicle's ecosystem, which is rapidly growing nowadays and represent an essential step towards a more sustainable future. The developed algorithm could be integrated into the next ISO 15118 versions or implemented by companies to prevent the exploitation of this category of threats.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

Even if this expedition took place remotely, the support from the University of Washington was fundamental. Their knowledge and equipment were very helpful during the research. Furthermore, we started a profitable collaboration that we will expand with a visiting period during my Ph.D.

GAL MORGENSTERN

PROJECT

Graph-based power system state estimation subsequent to cyber-attack detection

FOCUS AREA

Cybersecurity

CHALLENGE

While they vastly improve power systems operation, advanced cyber-communication systems are highly vulnerable to cyber threats. Specifically, the vulnerability to a wide group of attacks referred to as FDIs is significantly detrimental given their ability to bypass the current bad data detection methods installed in power utilities. Although most studies give reasonable solutions to single attacks at a single timestamp, they are not adequate for the case in which multiple measurements in multiple consecutive timestamps are compromised. Thus, existing methods provide only a partial solution to real-world attack scenarios. Therefore, the challenge addressed was coping with the power system's vulnerability to FDIs.

KEY RESULTS

A key result of this collaboration is a designed framework for identifying sequences of FDI attacks, which, as argued above, are a primary concern in designing modern electrical power grids. The proposed framework exploits graphical and quasi-static modeling of power system state variables. Another result is a set of novel methods for identifying sophisticated FDI attacks. Applying these methods facilitates the correction of compromised measurements, enabling resilient operation. Future work includes theoretical and empirical analysis in multiple settings.

IMPACT

The proposed methodologies increase the cyber security level of power systems. Specifically, they render modern power grids more resilient to complex FDI sequence attacks at a reduced cost compared to alternatives.

Due to similar underlying modeling, the potential the proposed tools have on other disciplines (e.g., biology) is very high and is to be tried in future work.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

This experience of collaborating with Prof. Gil Zussman and, consequently, with additional specialists from the industry and Columbia University has been highly beneficial to the research conducted and my personal development. The wide range of research fields covered by the collaborating researchers provided insights that significantly improved the design of the proposed solutions. Moreover, exposure to a different mentoring style provided by Prof. Zussman opened my mind to various research and life management methodologies.

Future collaboration is currently being initiated where both parties show interest in publishing a joint paper on the discussed subject to a high-quality journal.

SANDIP DAS

PROJECT

Investigate Optical Wireless Integration Technologies for Next-generation Converged Access Networks detection

FOCUS AREA

5G

CHALLENGE

Ultra-low end-to-end latency with high reliability is one of the most important requirements in 5G telecom networks to support the next generation telecom applications that are highly end-to-end delay-sensitive such as tactile internet, logistics, and mission-critical-control. In order to support these requirements, the integration between wireless access and optical transport networks has been one of the main focus point that calls for significant architectural innovation. Since the fronthaul transport for the 4th generation radio access network is based on point-to-point fibre, with the progressive cell densification at 5G, building a cost-effective fronthaul transport becomes a major issue. Passive Optical Networks (PON) which has primarily been used to provide residential broadband access is now being looked upon as a potential solution to provide fronthaul transport, as it can already use the existing deployed fibres with much greater scalability and cost-effectivity. In this project therefore, we investigate the Optical (PON)-Wireless integration for next-generation converged access for 5G and beyond. We especially look to address the problem from real-world systems perspective in order to demonstrate the feasibility/proof-of concept of such solutions.

KEY RESULTS

Following key results were obtained during the course of the expedition.

- An Optical-wireless converged architecture for enabling differentiated 5G services with cost-effectivity.
- Demonstrated the feasibility of PON-wireless integration experimentally by integrating PON based fronthaul over LTE/NR wireless cells.
- Real-time performance results were obtained with this optical-wireless converged experimental set up.
- Successful demonstration of vBBU migration experiment on the experimental set up.

IMPACT

Utilizing PON as fronthaul transport for RAN is gaining attraction owing to its cost-effectiveness as compared to other optical solutions. The research on this area is emerging and has a lot of potential to see commercial adaptability. This successful initial working set up of PON-wireless integrated architecture, opens up a diverse set of envisioned experimentation for potential technical contribution in the state-of-the-art. Therefore, this work would provide a first reference point to carry out further innovation to help the technology to get matured.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

With this remote expedition for 3 months, this project saw a collaboration between US node (USC) and EU node (TCD) on investigation and initial feasibility demonstration of optical-wireless integrated architecture. The technical expertise and support received from the US node has been very beneficial throughout the duration of the project. The outcomes from the project has opened some exciting research directions that foresees a further collaboration which is currently ongoing even after the completion of the original expedition.

SERENA LEKA

PROJECT

The use of AI for idea management to assist radical innovation in new product development: Case of US firms

FOCUS AREA

5G

CHALLENGE

Enterprises nowadays, of all sizes, are investing a lot of resources in identifying and implementing the next big idea. What at first seems like a mix of innovation activities, at later stages it becomes a rather complex and time-consuming process, not necessarily providing the right results. Idea management systems (IMS) are part of the solution as the means to organize stakeholder ideas in one platform. A hybrid approach to idea management is superior to sole computational evaluations or sole human decisions.

Data presented via all these innovation contributions in the form of ideas require managing to avoid two major pitfalls: constraints in processing information and ineffective ideas from the local routine searches. The project's ambition is to offer a novel method for managing new product development (NPD) ideas in firms via AI as the toolbox.

KEY RESULTS

- Widening knowledge: during the 5-month hybrid collaboration, participated in about +20 events/classes/conferences/workshops in the area of innovation & AI;
- Data gathering for survey results: 2 databases were identified and organized, summing up to having contact details for more than 500 companies in North Carolina;
- Project advances: based on the professional interactions, we decided that Rosetta, the IMS we have developed so far, will unfold into a spin-out from Aarhus University.

IMPACT

Bringing Rosetta to enterprises will provide the following impact:

- Open innovation, empowered by AI will provide faster access to gathering new knowledge, thus increasing innovation capacity;
- Creating competitive and financial benefits by promoting the flexibility of Rosetta as IMS as it democratizes innovation activities for enterprises;
- Increasing employee/stakeholder motivation and organizational efficiency in promoting innovation skills.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

RENCI at UNC-Chapell Hill has opened the doors to the Research Triangle Area and supported me to follow leads in building collaborations with the local industry for future designated case studies. The collaboration with RENC I will continue in the coming years, as we have initiated project discussions with the "twin" institution in Tokyo, Japan, namely RIKEN.

GREG AGRIPOULOS

PROJECT

Can you imagine physical interaction with limited touch capabilities?

FOCUS AREA

IoT

CHALLENGE

Magos (a wearable: mixture of textile, mechanical and electrical parts) is a high-tech wearable solution with unique technical characteristic in the Human Computer Interaction (HCI) sector.

It is comprised by the hardware part - the gloves - and the software tool - the middleware and the unique interactions platform. Magos unique value proposition is its great accuracy in finger tracking, something that constitutes the game changer for the haptics subsystem, entirely revolutionizing the user experience.

Those unique technical characteristics are the driving factor to redefine the HCI in various sectors and applications (Virtual Reality, Robotics, Healthcare).

Due to the complexity of the HW the fast and reliable connectivity with a local device (PC) is of major Importance to deliver a top of the market solution. US node will support towards this direction with their expertise and resources.

KEY RESULTS

US node utilized their vast experience and knowledge around the IoT connectivity and protocols and actively supported the design and specifications setup phase.

The result is a new and custom wireless communication protocol for the connection of the Magos gloves with a local PC.

IMPACT

Magos provides an advanced way of Human Computer Interaction, so, with a robust wireless communication Magos offerings will be clear to potential customers providing new technological solutions in various areas and sectors (virtual training and simulation in aerospace-healthcare, robotics).

Via this project, Magos is able to reach to the next level - customer engagement with advanced user experience.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

US market is of huge importance for our strategy, so a collaboration with Santa Clara University was a great start for our US journey.

Magos already has some traction to US corporates, so, the collaboration with a US university provides credibility.

GÜRGEN LEVENT

PROJECT

Experimenting an edge-computing based AI approach for safe and efficient intersections in urban areas

FOCUS AREA

IoT

CHALLENGE

In Europe and in US, an important percentage of all traffic deaths and injuries occur at intersections. There is an urgent need for better management of intersections in urban areas, which has considerable social, economic and environmental impact.

The emerging technologies such as IoT, AI, 5G, etc. can help building intersections with smart features such as detecting dangerous situations and better managing traffic jams. However, we still need to experiment and validate those smart solutions in terms of accuracy, latency, privacy, user acceptance, etc., in real life settings, which is complex and costly to setup.

KEY RESULTS

The project built an experimentation framework to test smart intersection applications on top of Kentyou's smart city platform and Columbia University's testbed setting in Manhattan, NYC. The testbed provides data captured by security cameras at intersections, accessible by Kentyou's common API, which provides real-time, historic and predictive information about dangerous situations at the intersections.

Furthermore, Kentyou built a dashboard that provides useful insights about the intersection's past current and future status (traffic speed, number of vehicles per type, red light violations, average crossing times for pedestrians, etc.) by applying AI and machine learning for predictive analysis.

IMPACT

The project has been dealing with an important social, economic, and environmental problem: safety and efficiency of intersections.

The project tackled the problem by facilitating building and validating smart intersection experiments with an open and interoperable framework. It provides a common API under specific data models including raw and processed data from the intersections. It also provided a set of visual elements to allow city traffic management division to oversee the intersections and react on events occurring at intersections.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

As a next step, data will openly be provided to experimenters under upcoming joint collaboration opportunities between Kentyou and Columbia University. We have identified several future opportunities, in particular in the context of the Urban Technology Alliance (www.urbantechnologyalliance.org) and upcoming calls from the NGI Atlantic programme and related Horizon Europe calls. The framework will allow future developers building safety and efficiency applications for the ultimate goal of saving lives and reducing carbon emissions caused by the traffic.

LUIS DE LA TORRE CUBILLO

PROJECT

Remote-Controlled Access to Internet of Things Devices

FOCUS AREA

IoT

CHALLENGE

Online labs (OLs) are research or educational lab systems (either virtual or real) that can be used remotely. Their usefulness has already been demonstrated in several contexts by many works, and have gain special prominence in the pandemic situation. However, this type of Internet of Things (IoT) labs have not been adopted massively so far. This is because they are more difficult and demanding to develop and many institutions lack the staff to do so. In this sense, two of the most limiting factors are: 1) a web application and user interface (UI) must usually be developed and 2) borrowing or renting already existing OLs from other institutions is not easy due to the lack of an efficient and systematized process.

KEY RESULTS

- A framework to automatically create UIs based on IoT-type metadata was designed.
- A real and working implementation of the framework was achieved.
- A servo-motor online lab was used as a test-case and a UI was automatically built using the above framework and implementation.
- A paper presenting the previous achievements was submitted to an international journal in January 2022.
- A specification of a smart contract to share online labs through blockchain technologies was prepared to support the exchange of OLs.

IMPACT

In the social aspect:

- Learners can perform lab activities from their homes, which enhance safety when working with dangerous equipment, provides more lab time (and so, enhances the overall learning process), improves adaptability to students' schedules, facilitates lab work to handicapped people, and offers a viable solution for lab work in pandemic situations.
- Researchers can also perform lab work at distance, with similar advantages.

At a technological level:

- IoT-type metadata coming from OLs is used to automatically build the UIs of the web applications that allow monitoring and manipulating the lab resources.
- The proposed smart contract specification is intended to be presented as an EIP for blockchain standard.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

On the one hand, the US partner had experience with blockchain, whereas I had not, so it was very insightful for the smart contract specification. On the other hand, having a partner overseas to be able to try and test resulting OLs applications in the future, at thousands of Kms of distance, provides a great test. Finally, a joint paper for publication has been already prepared (on the automatic generation of UIs) and a second one (on the blockchain use for sharing OLs) is expected.

RIDHA AZAIZ

PROJECT

MaMa - Martian Maintenance

FOCUS AREA

IoT

CHALLENGE

Arizona is home to four different deserts, which sees more sunlight than most other regions in the US and is ideally situated for solar power. With the state being among the driest in the country, solar panels suffer soiling from dust.

The explorer developed a robot that utilizes airflow to clean the solar glass without water. The higher output of this maintenance will then be feed to digital ledger technologies (DLT). With this the robots' impact could be recorded securely - the basis for new business models.

KEY RESULTS

- A ground robot to remove contaminant from surfaces using object detection with vision computing was developed. Operational characteristics of the cleaning process are then processed by a software back-end that will be running in the cloud.
- Arizona State University has several solar installations on campus, on which promising impact of the airflow cleaning method was observed. Hence the mission was extended to built and install a test stand that records soiling and cleaning levels, year-round.

IMPACT

- Scarcity of fresh water is a reoccurring issue in Southwest of the US and many other countries that suffer drought. We demonstrated how an airflow cleaning solution that fuses robotics, DLT's and cloud computing could help to save resources but also increase renewable energy production.
- The cleaning method was already observed on Mars (hence the projects' name) with its storms. The project enables us to quantify the impact a sustained maintenance could have on earth.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

- Unlike ground robots - drones produce airflow, naturally. Anyhow autonomous flight of drones (unmanned aerial vehicles) is currently prohibited for commercial purpose in many countries.
- The explorer produced a ground robot that can achieve similar results without being subject to airspace regulations. Initial research showed the promising impact the technology could have in the region and a follow up project was fostered.

ROBERTO MEDINA BUJALANCE

PROJECT

Transmit one bit the longest using the least power utilizing LoRa

FOCUS AREA

IoT

CHALLENGE

This project aims to solve connectivity problems encountered in the USA and part of the world; utilizing LoRa as the radio technology; we provided solutions for environmental monitoring, livestock, fires, earthquakes, or natural disasters in the beginning while working on a complete prototype for remote patient monitoring in the medical field.

KEY RESULTS

We were able to design a device, manufacture and test it. Deploy a LoRaWAN network, obtain the data and visualize it in software installed on the cloud. Our solution is a testbed for future applications for remote monitoring, sensors, or actuators. Thanks to our achievements, we integrated our design into a medical device and started to do some tests in Hospitals.

Our end-users are businesses, cities, or people who want to have long-range and ultra-low-power devices that can maintain themselves for a long time. Thanks to this technology, every company that manufactures a product based on LoRaWAN standard can take their data to the exact visualization and enhance the data models and use other technologies for improving the way of monitoring sensors.

IMPACT

It directly impacts how the products could integrate into different use cases, primarily agricultural and medical. The farming case helps to monitor and make smart irrigation in large areas with low coverage of LTE or other technologies, giving many possibilities to the industry. For medical, it helps develop patient monitoring and is non-interfere with Wi-Fi or other technologies already deployed into the hospital.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

It was a fantastic experience that showed me how the USA's University, Industry, and Business works. Furthermore, I enjoyed meeting with local companies, understanding their problems, and solving them.

My experience with Sonoma State University was excellent. I was introduced to the faculties, personal and different students, visiting other Universities like Santa Clara or Berkeley.

The best thing I have achieved here is to create friendships and connections with people I see the future possibility of doing business or visiting again to do other types of research.

Working with a medical startup opened the possibility of introducing "Made in the Europe" to the USA market, and I wish we could improve and have a product this year.

I now have a new perspective of Europe's strengths and weaknesses compared to the USA. I have seen them too in myself, being more conscious of becoming a better entrepreneur and businessman through improving.

RODION DENISYUK

PROJECT

eyeGauge – easy digitalization

FOCUS AREA

IoT

CHALLENGE

Modern AI technologies for Computer Vision require a lot of processing power and are usually executed in the Cloud. However, this limits the application of those technologies due to power and connectivity availability in remote areas. Privacy concerns are also being raised nowadays related to processing of data in the Cloud.

A possibility to run machine learning vision algorithms directly on the field, on hundreds of battery-powered long-range devices opens up a new field of applications for AI. Emergence of a technology called TinyML makes it possible and the corresponding use cases can now be explored.

KEY RESULTS

The goal of this project was development of a hardware and software platform for execution of computer vision deep learning algorithms for use cases requiring deployments of smart devices in environments with limited power and connectivity options or sensitive to privacy issues.

Together with participants from Sonoma State University and IMT Atlantique university in France we created a platform that can be used to build devices for real-life use cases.

Unfortunately, restrictions on entry to the USA affected the possibility to meet local businesses and potential clients in California. Nevertheless, we were able to identify interesting use cases and collect the first feedback from stake holders. The use cases we worked on were:

- Nature preservation
- Sustainable agriculture
- Public spaces monitoring

IMPACT

TinyML is an emerging technology making its first steps in commercialization. We selected the “vision” component of machine learning because it has the biggest application scope but is also the most challenging for implementation on small devices.

Apart from purely commercial applications, we also discovered environmental (wildlife monitoring) and sustainability (reduction of insecticide usage in agriculture) use cases that have a great potential of development for the good of the society.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

We want to highlight the successful collaboration between EYEGAUGE team and SSU professors, staff, and students.

We are looking forward to a very close collaboration with SSU in the nearest future. We have a prototype that is almost ready for deployment, and we have use cases and businesses in California interested in seeing this solution applied.

SOUMYA KANTI DATTA

PROJECT

Secure, interoperable, automatic data portability for IoT (SPIRIT)

FOCUS AREA

IoT

CHALLENGE

Healthcare services and mHealth app like AMICA developed by DigiTouch (DIGI) powered by its Cloud, Paradise Platform require access to patient's vital parameters and physical activity data generated by wearable devices (e.g., Withings ScanWatch). Although COVID-19 has accelerated adoption of digital solutions, healthcare data portability from wearable device manufacturers' cloud platform (e.g., Withings cloud) to service cloud platforms like DIGI's Paradise Platform is still non-automatic, non real time, insecure, and fragmented. To break healthcare data silos, enable users to take control of their data, and be compliant with GDPR Article 20 on data portability, European healthcare industry must support data portability. SPIRIT has solved this data portability challenge and will disrupt the European healthcare industry with its end-to-end, interoperable, secure, privacy-by-design, and automatic data portability tool for IoT based healthcare services.

KEY RESULTS

The project delivered a digital tool for automatic data portability for IoT based healthcare services and an MVP demonstration. The MVP of SPIRIT has been demonstrated with a healthcare data portability business case from DigiTouch. The tool has been integrated with DigiTouch's cloud based Paradise Platform extending its capabilities for smart healthcare services.

IMPACT

SPIRIT project significantly extends the technical state-of-the-art in the data portability area. As explained, SPIRIT tool solves a market-driven problem on healthcare data portability. Apart from the technical impact, SPIRIT tool will have a positive societal impact enabling general public to take control on their healthcare and fitness data and decide how to move that among healthcare service providers. The developed tool will be further utilised in DigiTouch's healthcare business cases.

US COLLABORATION BENEFITS

The project has been performed in collaboration between DigiTouch, an European SME and State University of New York at Binghamton, a US node. DigiTouch foresees extending such collaboration for such future transatlantic funding calls.

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